

First record of *Myopthiria zeylanica* Maa, 1980 (Diptera: Hippoboscidae) from India

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Abstract: *Myopthiria* is a highly specialised genus of brachypterous hippoboscids parasitising swifts and swiftlets (Apodidae). *Myopthiria zeylanica* Maa, 1980 has been considered endemic to Sri Lanka. Here we report the first record of *M. zeylanica* from India, based on a single female collected from an Indian swiftlet (*Aerodramus unicolor* (Jerdon, 1840)) found dead during a field visit in the Nilgiri Hills, Tamil Nadu, at 2238 m a.s.l. The specimen was identified based on external morphology following Maa (1980). This record provides new distributional data for this rarely collected swiftlet-associated louse-fly.

Keywords: Apodidae, host association, louse fly, new distributional data

Introduction

Hippoboscids of the genus *Myopthiria* are highly specialised, brachypterous (flightless), and superficially spider-like parasites (Maa, 1980). They exhibit extreme host specificity toward swifts and swiftlets (Apodiformes: Apodidae), primarily the

genera *Collocalia* in the Old World and *Aeronautes* in the New World (Bequaert, 1954; Maa, 1969, 1980).

The genus *Myopthiria* is characterised by a head that is consistently longer than wide, with significantly reduced eyes (approximately 2/7 the length of the head), and with the absence of ocelli. Wings are reduced to pad-like structures with

Fig. 1. Indian swiftlet (*Aerodramus unicolor* (Jerdon, 1840)) found dead along the roadside.

simplified venation, where veins M_{1+2} , M_{2+3} and Cu_1+A typically coalesce into a thickened stem (Maa, 1980).

The genus is divided into two subgenera: *Myophthiria* s. str. (Old World) and *Brachypteromyia* (New World) (Maa, 1980). Dick (2018) listed 13 species in the genus, including three Old World species, two New World species, and eight incertae sedis taxa. Zootaxonomically, the Old World species are remarkably uniform in structure and body size, necessitating the use of “quantitative” characters and relative measurements for species identification. The key features of the *Myophthiria* s. str. subgenus include palpus subequal in length to the antenna, a scutellum bearing 4–10 bristles in a single transverse series, the presence of 1 or 2 pairs of vertical bristles, and a head that is widest behind the level of the eyes (Maa, 1980).

The aim of this study is to document the first record of *Myophthiria zeylanica* Maa, 1980 from India and provide basic data on this specific organism.

Material and methods

During a regular field visit in the Nilgiris, Tamil Nadu, India, a freshly dead Indian Swiftlet (*Aerodramus unicolor* (Jerdon, 1840)) was found on the roadside (Fig. 1; cause of death unknown) in a habitat dominated by *Eucalyptus* and tea plantations. A single hippoboscid fly was observed leaving the nape region of the bird and was collected and photographed after it reached the ground. The bird was not handled. The fly was identified based on external morphology following Maa (1980). Material is deposited in the ethanol collection of the Ongil Nature Conservation Trust for study purposes*. Sample was photographed using an RF4 4K Ultra HD Industrial Camera.

* Note: At present, this study is based on a single specimen; therefore, full preservation and formal deposition have not yet been completed. Additional field sampling is planned, and any newly collected material will be preserved following standard protocols and deposited in a recognised repository such as the BNHS Museum.

Results

Diptera: Hippoboscidae

Myophthiria zeylanica Maa, 1980 (Fig. 2)

Material examined: India, Tamil Nadu, Ooty, Nilgiri Hills, 11°24'36"N, 76°41'42"E, 2238 m a.s.l., 4 Feb 2026, 1 ♀, host: ex *Aerodramus unicolor* (Jerdon, 1840).

Distribution and ecology

Myophthiria zeylanica has been considered until now endemic to Sri Lanka (formerly Ceylon). While most Old World species are confined to lowlands below 600 metres, *M. zeylanica* is an exception, occurring in highland regions up to 1520 m a.s.l. (Maa, 1980).

The species is typically recovered from the nests or bodies of its primary hosts: the Indian edible-nest swiftlet (*Aerodramus fuciphagus* (Thunberg, 1812)) and the Indian swiftlet (*Aerodramus unicolor* (Jerdon, 1840)). Due to their flightless nature and specialised habitat, these flies are rare in collections and difficult to collect outside of host nesting sites (Maa, 1980). *Myophthiria zeylanica* was known only from Sri Lanka: type locality: Hunasgiriya, and from Namunukula, Uva Hills (Hindagalla Cave), Ella (Rawanaella Cave), and Pundaluoya and Gintota.

This is a new geographical record for the fauna of India (see also Maity et al., 2014).

Diagnostic features

According to Maa (1980), *M. zeylanica* belongs to the *zeylanica* subgroup (Subgroup 1a). The species is most reliably separated from other Old World taxa by male genital characters; however, the examined female matches the diagnostic external morphology given by Maa (1980), including the head is approximately 1.42 times as long as wide, and the vertex is distinctly longer than the combined lunula and interantennal region. The interantennal area is as wide as its distance to the inner orbit. In the wing, the vein R_{2+3} is present and clearly developed, although it is weaker than veins R_1 and R_{4+5} . The thorax is further characterised by the anterior margin of the mesobasis-

Fig. 2. Female of *Myophthiria zeylanica* Maa, 1980, collected in Nilgiris, parasitising Indian swiftlet (*Aerodramus unicolor* (Jerdon, 1840)).

ternum, which is narrowly rounded, produced medially, and shows a distinct submedian sinuation. Finally, the chaetotaxy provides supporting diagnostic information, as the setae and bristles on the dorsal connexivum are markedly finer than those on the thoracic dorsum.

Discussion

Although the genera *Myophthiria* and *Crataerina* (including *Stenepteryx hirundinis* (Linnaeus, 1758)) are both placed within Ornithomyiinae (Dick, 2018) and share several external similarities, the two genera can be readily confused by non-specialists, particularly when specimens are examined superficially (see Fig. 3). This potential for misidentification is further increased by their broadly comparable ectoparasitic lifestyle and host-associated adaptations, especially in taxa associated with Apodidae and Hirundinidae (Maa, 1980). Nevertheless, detailed morphological examination reveals a consistent set of characters that allows reliable separation (see Maa, 1963, 1980). In

Fig. 3. Overview of the basic differences between the females of genus *Myophthiria* (M1–M4) and genus *Crataerina* (C1–C4). 1. Head. 2. Thorax. 3. Wing. 4. Abdomen.

Myophthiria, the head is distinctly longer than wide (Fig. 3 M1), whereas in *Crataerina* head proportions are more variable and may approach a subquadrate condition (Fig. 3 C1). Eye reduction is also more pronounced in *Myophthiria*, with the eyes measuring approximately two-sevenths of head length (Fig. 3 M1), while in *Crataerina* they may reach up to one-half of head length (Fig. 3 C1). Thoracic morphology provides additional diagnostic traits: the median, notal and transverse mesonotal sutures are frequently obsolete in *Myophthiria* (Fig. 3 M2), either partially or completely, but remain at least partly defined in *Crataerina* (Fig. 3 C2). Wing morphology is similarly informative, as *Myophthiria* typically exhibits roundish, pad-like wings (Fig. 3 M3), in contrast to the ribbon-like or elongate wings characteristic of *Crataerina* (Fig. 3 C3). Venational

reduction is also more extensive in *Myophthiria*, where the relevant vein R_{2+3} is often indistinct and veins M_{1+2} , M_{2+3} , and Cu_1+A typically coalesce into a single thickened $MCuA$ stem (Fig. 3 M3). Further differences can be observed in the appendages: leg stoutness varies among species of *Myophthiria*, whereas it is consistently robust in *Crataerina*. Finally, female abdominal sclerotisation provides decisive characters, as the supra-anal plate is usually present in *Myophthiria* but entirely absent in *Crataerina*, and the seventh tergite in female *Myophthiria* is often represented by paired sclerites (Fig. 3 M4), whereas in *Crataerina* the corresponding tergite is broad, heavily sclerotised, and integrated into the terminal abdominal region rather than appearing as a separate, narrow plate (Fig. 3 C4).

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor. As a member of the editorial board Jozef Oboňa recused himself from discussions and decisions on the manuscript.

Author' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Jozef Oboňa: investigation, methodology, writing—original draft; Nizamudheen Moinudheen: investigation, methodology, writing—original draft; Arockianathan Samson: investigation, writing—original draft; Kesavan Rishi: investigation, writing—original draft; Anbazhagan Abinesh: investigation, writing—original draft; Elangovan Vignesh: investigation, writing—original draft; Mohammed Shahir: investigation, writing—original draft; Azad Kamil: investigation, writing—original draft.

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